

Analysis of National Education Policy 2020: Challenges & Opportunities

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Abstract

National education policy 2020 is the first policy which incorporates holistic approach start from school level to college education, it is more flexible, multidisciplinary and holistic which helps to inculcate unique abilities in each students. NEP based on how to make this principles NEP more accessible, equitable, affordable and accountable. National education policy provides compulsory schooling from 6 – 14 to 3 – 18; which includes 3 years of pre schooling for children ages 3 – 6. NEP promotes bilingual approach including teaching learning material at school level. NEP provided the structure of 10+2 school curriculum, vocational & academic streams, focus on conceptual understanding rather rote learning, it encourages digitalisation in education for making education open & accessible to all, using competency driven learning approach, assure quality education at universities in Indian education system, promote hybrid vocational education. This paper explores the significance of NEP'20 , impact on education system, furthermore, this paper study and discuss the challenges, opportunities and it's impact on states.

Key words: National Education policy, holistic approach, inclusivity, multidisciplinary

1. Introduction

National education policy 2020¹ revolves around the idea of flexibility, accessibility and accountability and support Multidimensional approach, NEP replaced with 5+3+3+4 idea of school curriculum. Emphasize on Early childhood care and education and foundation literacy numeracy; viewed art & science as a same, involves extra curricular activities with vocational and academic streams, emphasize on conceptual understanding rather focus on rote learning, it encourages digitalisation in education; integrate teacher education programme; which make education available to all, support internationalisation of universities in Indian education system; promote hybrid vocational education. Support National Education technical forum & new technology,

¹Kumar, Kishore, Prakash Ajai & Singh, Krishanveer., (2021). How national education policy 2020 can be a lodestar to transform future generation in India. *Journal of Public Affairs* 21 (3), e2500

evidence based policy for data driven system and enhanced digital infrastructure. India has over 1/6 of human force representation on the global map and it should contribute strongly to the global development in sync with the human force representation on earth.¹ New National Education Policy 2020 of India provides a comprehensive framework from primary education to higher education, vocational & technical education and a new paradigm of internet based e – learnings.²

National Education Policy focus on home language, mother tongue, local language & regional language as a medium of instruction; this strategy followed by both public & private schools. Distinction of science, arts & commerce get vanished. No distinction found between arts & science, curricular & extra curricular activities or vocational and academic programs under NEP 2020. Introduce FYUP programme as vocational & professional fields, colleges.

This system bring more transparency & a single national agency in charge which over seeing the whole education system in the country. Ensure holistic development of all students. Prepare foundational stage which is divided into two parts, classes 1& 2 in primary school. At this stage, children are require to learn in their local language and the curriculum includes subjects like writing, reading, speaking, Physical education, art, science & mathematics. Teachers will get fair chance to get promoted. No hard separations between art & science. Establish National Mission on foundational literacy & Numeracy. It encourages creativity and critical thinking to promote logical decision making and innovation. Author expressed his idea of education through creativity, collective thoughts for bringing powerful vision for natural talent to the world of education (Robinson, 2009).³ John Dewey stressed on school education based on modern educational theory; which involves themes & issues relating to education, teaching, learning, educational environments, subject matter, values and nature of work & play (Dewey, 2015).⁴

National Education Policy focuses on core values and kind of principle that education must develop not only the cognitive skills that is foundational skills of literacy and numeracy and higher order of skills such as critical thinking and problem solving infact involves social and emotional skills to as soft skills including cultural awareness and empathy perseverance, teamwork, leadership & communication. NEP aim to universalise the primary education and provides special emphasis on the attainment of foundational literacy & numeracy in primary schools.

² Aktar, Serena., (2021). *New education policy 2020 of India: A theoretical analysis. International Journal of Business & Management Research* 9 (3), 302 -306

³ Robinson, Ken., (2009). *The Element: How finding your passion changes everything. New York: Viking*

⁴ Dewey, John., (2015). *Democracy & education. Cambridge University Press*

Policy has few features such as:

- 1) Reform the current exam and assessment system
- 2) Strengthening of teacher training
- 3) Restructuring the education regulatory framework
- 4) Increase public investment in education
- 5) Strengthen the use of technology
- 6) Increase focus on vocational & adult education
- 7) Introduce core essential content

1.1 Acceptance of National Education Policy in different states

Tamil Nadu government are against of National Education Policy 2020, same with Telangana & West Bengal, on the basis of language, suggested states has linguistic barriers based on social, political & linguistic reasons, however, states agreed on four year level plan (5+3+3+4) which is divided on four levels: Foundational, Preparatory, Middle & Secondary; reluctant to bring changes on school level. Kerala, Karnataka & Tamil Nadu completely opposed NEP, West Bengal & Telangana resist to implement NEP only on the basis of language. Introduce programmes like Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan & PM SHRI aligned with NEP. Few states such as Bihar, Delhi, Rajasthan, Telangana and West Bengal only implemented few points of NEP as per their social & economic conditions. For instance, Andhra Pradesh government adopted a plan which revive the quality of teachers as per the NEP guidelines.

AAP restructure the school education from the next academic session. West Bengal government asked state universities to introduce four year programme (FYP) from upcoming academic session; however, made a clear cut point that not going to implement completely in their education system; subsequently, Haryana, Assam & Gujarat became first to implement the NEP.

2. Impact of National Education Policy

The objective of National Education Policy 2020 to make educational system more inclusive, learner centred, open, accessible and responsible. Here are few significant element of NEP such as:

- 1) Curriculum of NEP focus on foundational skills, cognitive knowledge, learner centred rather emphasize on teacher oriented education structure, build a framework which support students that helps to improve the inclusivity through play based learning, hands on lessons and integrating technology and focus more on vocational & multidisciplinary education.
- 2) Assessment means when union government centralised one agency to conduct the examination for all.

- 3) 13% states face the crisis of qualified secondary level teachers; NEP prepare a structure for constant training & support their teaching training with financial assistance.⁵
- 4) University management involves more freedom and better management to improve and innovate the educational system.
- 5) Financial assistance includes National research foundation to coordinate research funding to peer reviewed research. AICTE Saksham & AICTE Saksham are part of the NEP scheme 2020, scholarship are provided to those who are financially disadvantaged, special scholarships are provided to those who are from Jammu & Kashmir and Ladakh. Scholarships like central sector scheme of scholarship assigned in NEP 2020. Educational loans provide through credit guarantee fund scheme for education loan (CGFSEL) as this

scheme also part of PM – USP Yojana, NEP involves several education institutions, universities and organizations for loans and scholarships. External scholarship scheme such as commonwealth master's scholarship for UK, other foreign universities assign certain amount as scholarship under NEP scheme for Indian students; special inclusion funds are given to those who are in special needs of incentives and provided direct cash support and indirect in-kind support.⁶

- 6) NEP impact university management which aim to make the curriculum more flexible, focus on experiential learning; Reduce the burden of curricular content and maintain the flexibility for art & science, curricular and extracurricular activities, vocational & academic streams, and create more options according to students interests and talents. NEP promotes multidisciplinary knowledge & institutional autonomy. NEP set a goal that by 2030 entire educational system will become multidisciplinary. It encourages international collaborations as foreign universities provides loans & scholarships on certain amount at university level.

Allow indian universities & institutions to collaborate with foreign universities and introduce faculty based exchange programs. NEP more focus on digitalisation of education, encourage colleges to support online & blended learning experience to students. It proposes the idea to establish National Education Technical Forum (NETF) to promote technological innovation in education enhance classroom processes and teacher development.

⁵ <https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/in/pdf/2020/08/impact-of-national-education-policy-2020-and-opportunities-for-stakeholders.pdf>

⁶ Kurien, Ajay., B. Sandeep & B. Chandramana., (2020). *Impact of New Education Policy 2020 higher education*. Researchgate

3. *Challenges of National Education Policy*

- 1) Budget is a biggest problem of NEP, lack of funding slow down the implementation process as policy require certain amount for investment in infrastructure, teacher training and curriculum development; providing quality education in remote & rural areas and require need for effective collaboration between various stakeholders.
- 2) Policy stresses on the teacher training and development, existing teacher education system needs to revamped to create the changing needs of the education system.
- 3) Policy aim to make education inclusive and accessible to all but there are several challenges in achieving this goal. The existing education system suffers from various forms of inequality including gender, socio economic and regional disparities.
- 4) Another challenge of NEP'20 is quality education, how to maintain quality in education system especially in remote areas. Each state has their own problem to implement policy in every part of the country. It requires to sustained and concerned effort by all stakeholders including policymakers, educators & students.
- 5) Implementation of policy is difficult due to investment, infrastructure & cooperation with stakeholders.
- 6) Cultural or language barriers is another challenge for states, NEP proposed the idea of three language formula, which has sparked controversy in few states and make implementation process difficult.
- 7) New assessment system focuses on the holistic development of the students; assessing new system is quite complex to implement in rural areas, excessive use of technology make the system slow and rigid.⁷

4. *Opportunities of New Education Policy*

- 1) New Education Policy has a capacity to bring systemic transformation, central government constitute steering committee which regulate meetings with state government for smooth running of the implementation process. This policy is helpful to strengthen the education system.
- 2) On the governance level, establish vocational education as an alternative career option to enhance the skill set of an individual.
- 3) State government in collaboration with district and other local bodies establish convergence with Right to Education, develop rationalisation framework for institutional restructuring and expanding the target for 15 years.

⁷ Biswas, Supriyo., (2023). *Opportunities and challenges NEP 2020*. Researchgate

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- 4) Improving the condition of teachers, National Council for teacher education DGT, NSDC introduce state faculty development mission, nodal centres in universities, provide online platforms to train college faculty members.
- 5) This policy support holistic development of education system, increase the use of technology and Universalisation.⁸
- 6) Integrate vocational education and technology, virtual labs, innovative ideas, flexible learning and cognitive knowledge.⁹
- 7) National Education Policy re – design vocational training structure & Support multidisciplinary educational environment. ICT based opportunities through participation in technology provisioning, infrastructure set ups and capability development programmes for academic & administrative purpose.
- 8) Develop credit based system, continuous learning focusing on the courses in collaboration with HEIs for developing meaningful, employment oriented programmes which is helpful to generate job opportunities.
- 9) NEP support curriculum and pedagogy methods, leverage activity based programs and experiential learning pedagogy will require to upgrade both physical & digital infrastructure to provide required space and resources to the learner.
- 10) Opportunity to foreign universities to establish campus in India, indian legislature allows almost 100 foreign universities to set up their campuses in India; such universities will be given autonomy with other autonomous institutions of India.
- 11) Financial services & financial technology to collaborate with the national scholarship portal to support, foster & track the progress of students receiving scholarships.
- 12) For inclusivity & accessibility using technology based supportive tools and language appropriate teaching & learning material will be available to assist specially abled students.

Conclusion

National Education Policy 2020 considered as revolutionizing scheme to uplift the education system of India which constantly running since the time of Colonial period. Previously, many NEP 2020 scheme introduced by Indian government but didn't not made reflective or long lasting change. However, NEP 2020 support holistic development, through new kind of strategies such as vocational training, digitalisation of education, increase collaboration with foreign universities,

⁸ Jadhav, Atul S., (2021). *Opportunities and challenges of NEP 2020. International Journal for multidisciplinary research (IJFMR)*

⁹ Singh, Kumar Gajendra & Jaiswal, Neeraj., (2024). *Challenges and opportunities for implementing NEP 2020 in the higher education sector: A comprehensive Analysis. Naveen Shodh Sansar, Vol.1, Issue XLV*

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provide financial aid, curriculum & pedagogy method, multidisciplinary education environment, teacher training facility, establish vocational education as an alternative career option to enhance the skill set of an individual. NEP marked curriculum as more flexible, focus on experiential learning; Reduce the burden of curricular content and maintain the flexibility for art & science, curricular and extracurricular activities, vocational & academic streams, and create more options according to students interests and talents. NEP promotes multidisciplinary knowledge & institutional autonomy. NEP support curriculum must be foundational based, help to increase cognitive knowledge, helps to improve the inclusivity through play based learning, hands on lessons and integrating technology and focus more on vocational & multidisciplinary education. The policy aims to provide more options aligned with students' interests and talents, fostering a more adaptable and inclusive educational environment.

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